

Civil Court – Housing Division, Queens NY: Transcript Request Report - 2025-11-19

An M. Rodriguez

November 23, 2025

1 One-Sentence Summary

Summary of the process and conditions for obtaining a hearing transcript in the Queens Housing Court.

2 Abstract

This report describes the steps required to request a transcript from a housing-court hearing in Queens, New York. It records the form requirements, expected delivery time, and cost estimates. The aim is to document the administrative process clearly for future reference.

3 Report Info

- Date: 2025-11-19
- Place: Queens, New York, USA

4 Keywords

transcript, court records, housing court, Queens NY

5 Introduction

This report documents the process of requesting a transcript from the Civil Court Housing Division in Queens, New York.

6 Observations

- Court open 9am–5pm

- Paper form needs to be filled in situ
- Form fields: index number, parties' names, date and hour of requested hearing
- Appeals have additional details to consider.
- Audio recording delivered by email, free. Staff estimated **4–6 weeks**, but it actually arrived within a few days.
 - Hearing (and thus the audio recording) lasts ~10 minutes.
- Transcript cost estimated around \$0.50 per minute (approximate, uncertain), if requested.

7 Discussion

- Process simple:
 - Could be automated online easily.
 - It is possible such automation already exists but is not clearly communicated.
- Reported times (4–6 weeks) for receiving the recording were greatly overestimated. The recording arrived within a few days.
 - This suggests staff may not have consistent or up-to-date information on timelines.

8 Conclusion

- Transcript request submitted
- Staff approximated audio delivery in 4–6 weeks, it was actually few days.
- Final transcription cost still approximate at \$0.5/page - whole transcript or nothing.
- Housing court timing and processes can be improved via more automation.
- Use of AI can provide a pseudo-transcript for free.

9 About Author(s)

An M. Rodriguez, an@preferredframe.com, <https://orcid.org/0009-0009-9098-9468>